
TRANSFORMING INDIA: PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT FOR TEACHER INICT

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Abstract:

The present paper has emphasis on professional development for teachers in ICT. Transforming India is possible through healthy education. We all are known that teachers are pillar of our society. The objective of this paper to study ICT use in professional development of a teacher. Sources of information from various article, reports thesis news paper etc. Teaching strategies will changes to ancient period to digital period help of ICT skills and accessibility, usability for transforming India. Teachers can build sound knowledge regarding subject as well as all round development.

Keywords: Professional, Development, Teacher, Students, ICT, Knowledge

Article History

*Received: 10/01/2021; Accepted: 27/01/2021

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Introduction:

Role of ICT in teaching learning in very essential for development of professional teachers. in our India many role model have present still now like Savatri bie Phulle, Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam, Radha krisan ji etc. on the other hand Rabindranath Tagore founder of Visva bharati, santiniketan ,Pandit Modan Mohan Malabaylaya who establish Banaras Hindu University for betterment our society through good and quality education. Now we are going through digital era and we are connected through the whole world by the help of internet. Any information in your hand within in a second.

The quality concern, teachers and continuing professional development on education, training is main central part to the achievement of quality professional development of teacher education. Yet today, different aspect like number of quality teachers, teaching practice and teacher education are facing serious systematic challenge across the world and mostly India. The situation will must be recovered at a time when the world need an estimated 17.8 million for primary new teachers education and 33.5 million for secondary new teachers education to reach international agreed education target by 2025 probably.

Information and Communication & Technology (ICT) is all time attached day to all activities for everybody. Now it's a big tools for the build a new generation learners to create his / her future.

NPE-1986 was introduce slowly ICT application for the teaching profession but we are know that rapidly change our study habit all over the world. NPE-2005 and now recently introduce another policy NEP-2020 told largely emphasis on ICT for professional development being a qualified teacher.

In the pandemic COVID-19 situation whole world facing lots of difficulties in education system everything was stopped for long time. Due to that causes largely effect on teaching learning process for all sectors like schools, colleges, universities, Research etc. but whose teacher not comfortable use on ICT tool for teaching learning process ,in that time those teacher understand how impotence ICT in teaching learning process.

ICT tools like computer, laptop, camera, white board, smart board, projector, and scanner various teaching learning apps (Google meet, Zooms,Jitsi, Cisco Web Exetc.) and others online teaching- learning platform apps like unacademy, khan academy, Vedantu, Indian Digital Library etc.

Need and Significance of the study:-

Transforming world can be change rapidly day by day so scenario of the teaching learning process classroom is changing. In our society have create a gap between technological progress of the society's needs and various instructional activities of the teacher in the teching learning process during classroom. If we are see revolutionary parameter needs to adopt new knowledge regarding ICT, flexibility to use and hand on experience classroom. Ancient period to Modern period instructional activities of a teacher is necessary to changes for inclusion classroom situation. In our classroom more attractive more real more gaining knowledge all round development of a children point of view is essential and its cant possible without using proper technological awareness of a teacher. 21st Century's education is student centric education from teacher centric. Students can learned fromdifferent sources and for this reason use of ICT is very much important in educational field.Simultaneously teacher's knowledge of ICT and Multimedia also needed. So thispresent study has very essential and significance because this study shows Transforming India: Professional Development for teacher in ICT.

2. Objectives:

To study the ICT skills use in Professional Development for teacher.

3. Methodology

Method used in Descriptive Analytic method. The pre3sent study is based on

secondary data only. Researcher collected data from different sources there are websites, journal articles, e-books reports, virtual observation of various organization and commission, articles published in local papers, national and international etc. This paper will give a brief description Transforming India: Professional Development for teacher in ICT.

According to our objectives here teacher, ICT, skills, professional, development etc. is most essential terms for brief description of this paper.

Why do we use ICT in Professional Development for teacher?

The classroom environment is now dynamic changing from the traditional way to digital way and one way to two way teaching learning process. Now students and teachers participate in the various activities like field based learning, blended learning, peer group learning and classroom discussion. New Education policy 2020 more emphasis on ICT based learning and classroom should be attractive and enjoyable for the learners. Teaching learning process is based on child centric education. So the teacher should be more prepared to adjust and flexible with use of different technology for creating enjoyable classroom environment. For effective implementation of ICT tools during class period for the student-centric methodologies such as peer group learning, project-based learning which puts more active role students, technology becomes play vital role and appropriate tool. It is an effective tool for information and knowledge to acquiring-from different kind of sources. Teacher should taking class attractive ways with the help of smart board, projector, slide share, internet etc. So for this reason ICT is very much necessary for development of professional Teacher.

Categories of professional teacher:

Preparation of Professional teacher can be classified into two category like...

- a. Pre-service teacher
- b. In-service teacher

During this two process of preparing of a good qualified Professional teacher must be acquired knowledge of ICT skills and proper use in the practical field in the sense class room. Here mention different kind of professional courses for preparing qualified teacher. Teachers need every time up dated and needs to modify teaching style for teaching learning process.

Recent Trends in professional Teacher in India:-

Recent trend being a professional teachers become more challenging job from the others jobs. Teacher should be qualified, knowledgeable, subject oriented student friendly flexible to use ICT tools and to create healthy environment during class room situation. Teacher is a pillar of our society according to our society's needs teaching strategies should changing time to time. Based on changing needs of our educational

policies more emphasis on various educational theory and educational practices. According to these theories and practices professional teacher modified his or her skills every time, and accept new ICT technology. Teachers should develop own attitude, aptitude, motivation, strength to facing different kind of problematic situation in our society as well as school environment.

As we know the minimum qualification of any training programme already mention different kind of policies and govt. bodies, like NCTA, NCFTE 2009 etc. it's should be helped the trainee to acquire the basic skills, knowledge and competencies of a good professional teacher. in recent trends in professional teacher education programme are multi-disciplinary, Inter-disciplinary Approach, Correspondence courses, ICT engagement, orientation courses etc. Different kind of activities like simulated Teaching, co-cultural activity, school observation, Micro Teaching, supervision class Programmed Instruction, Team Teaching and internship are also used to developed professional teacher. Action Research also implemented in the different type of courses in Teacher Education. ICT acts as the gateway to the transforming Indian teachers to be updated. It creates awareness of innovative trends in instructional methodologies, evaluation mechanism etc. for professional development.

Different courses for preparing teachers in India:-

Different Strategies for applying ICT in Professional Teacher development:-

- Providing proper and technical supporting system and suitable infrastructure
- All subjects has required ICT application based.

- By using different kind of ICT based application software, multimedia, student friendly software, Internet e-mail, storage capacity gadgets, communities, understanding system software for teachers.

New features for professional teacher development in India:

- Government of India has been initiative on **Microsoft Shiksha** in India; is mostly focused on using different kind of ICTs skill for training teachers. **Microsoft Shiksha** includes lots of features for training and applying a ICTs in their teaching practices.
- In our India, several initiatives programme are going on for creating new ICT skills and these digital repositories and have learningspecific objectives; The **Sakshat Portal** for Govt. of India initiative for quality and equality for all professional teacher development in the different level of education like the Teaching MERLOT (Multimedia Educational Resource for Learning and Online), NPTEL (National Program on Technology Education Learning).
- The objectives of *National Program on Technology Education Learning (NPTEL)* was to develop curriculum wise video lectures based and this particular course based on systemic web structured wise courses to enhance and build knowledge for quality of engineering education in India. This specific program became a great successful in the real ground oriented for across India by both public and private parties.

Advantages of ICT for professional development teachers and non-Teaching Staffs:-

- Using of ICT gadgets for teachers can easily represent through various platforms their lecture.
- Teachers can make their teaching learning process interesting, qualitative, assessable and fruitful by using ICT skills.
- Non-teaching staff can easily store the various records in institute's computers.
- Reduce isolation of teachers working space in the particular special education need by enabling them to communicate electronically with colleagues.
- Enhances the skill for professional development of teachers and use of ICT with students through collaboration during teaching learning process.
- Improving the different kind of skills for service staff greater understanding of access technology used by students.

Digital (ICT) Resources for Education

Popplet	Desktop and laptops	Pen Drive	Word processing
Tablets	Digital cameras	Microphones	Spreadsheets
Photocopy	Printer	DVDs and CDs	Presentation software
Android App	Animation	Web boards	World-wide Web

Various Initiatives for teachers and students ICT in education and teaching-learning

Sl.No.	Names	Names
1	Swayam Prabha	7. E-Basta
2	E-Granthalaya	8. Sugam Pustakalya
3	Digital Sakshrata Abhiyan (DISHA)	9. National Knowledge Network
4	Sala Sarathi	10. Shala Siddhi
5	National Super Computer Mission	11. National Scholarship
6	Shaala Darpan	12. Shaala Darpan

Role of ICT for professional development of Teacher transforming India

- In-Service teachers and pre service training teacher can easily use through ICT.
- Interaction between students and teachers will do any time
- ICT helps to prepare different kind of aids for their teaching learning process and, provide feedback.
- Teachers can access without any difficulties for any queries with institutions, UGC, NCERT, NCTE, Universities etc. through ICT.
- Create more attention and effectiveness during process of teaching learning with the help of various ICT tools.
- Teacher can improve his or her Teaching skill and create innovative Teaching classroom for learners.
- Improving the professional Development of teachers, Educational management skills and enhances new knowledge his or her Active Learning behaviour of teacher Trainees.
- Teachers and students more competitive use of updated information through of ICT.
- Teachers can collect various teaching materials from different sources of ICT.
- NCERT, NCTE can be developed their effective curriculum using ICT.
- ICT help to prepares real classroom situation for the learners.
- ICT can help to all kind of an “assisting tool” like attendance, distribution notes, feedback, assignment, project, evaluation, communication, documentation, conducting research etc.
- Institutions management skill and organisation should be done with the help of ICT.
- In the Digital locker students and teachers can lock his or her important documents help of ICT skills.
- Transforming the teaching methods traditional teaching to modern teaching skills.
- ICT can reduce the commutation gap between students- teachers.
- Teachers more updated and gain new information through the use of electronic gadgets.

Conclusion: Transforming India is possible when education play great role in our society and education will more powerful when professional teachers can teach properly. In the era of 21st century teaching style will be changed with the use of different kinds of ICT tools. Adaptation our knowledge from is now very easy to collect and collaborated with the classroom situation. New policies already told inclusive education have been provided all over the India. So in our classroom have present different kinds of learners can learn together and it is very difficult to manage

whole class during same time, here ICT can help to manage crate attention, attraction and proper guidance during teaching learning process. Digital materials can provide equality for every student free of cost or nominal charge. ICT (Information and communication Technology)provide to sound knowledge for teacher who will be developed his or her career be professional teacher.

References:

- Anamuah-Mensah, J. (2003). *Meeting the challenges of education in the twenty-first century*. Educational Reforms Commission. Accra, Ghana: Ministry of Education Youth & Sports. Retrieved May 5, 2020
- Wenglinski, H. (1998). *Does it compute? The relationship between educational technology and student achievement in mathematics*. Princeton, NJ: ETS.
- Beringer, V. (2009, October 20) *For kids, pen's mightier than keyboard*. Futurity.org. Retrieved May 25th 2020 from <http://www.futurity.org/society-culture/for-kids-pens-mightier-than-keyboard/#more-4909>.
- Adelsberger, H., Collis, B., & Pawlowski, J. (2002). *Handbook on information technologies for education and training*. Berlin: Springer-Verlag
- Baron, L. C., & Goldman, E. S. (1994). Integrating technology with teacher preparation. In B. Means (Ed.), *Technology and education reform* (pp. 81–110). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Publishers
- Betz, K. M., & Mitchell, J. W. (1996). Educational technology in teacher education. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, 4(3/4), 181–197.
- Bryman, A., & Cramer, D. (1997). *Quantitative data analysis with SPSS for Windows: A guide for social scientists*. London: Routledge.
- Brush, T., Glazewski, K., Rutowski, K., Berg, K., Stromfors, C., Van-Nest, M.H., Stock, L., & Sutton, C. (2003). Integrating technology in a field-based teacher training program: The PT3@ASU project. *Educational Technology and Research Development*, 51(1), 57–72
- Cronbach, L. J. (1990). *Essentials of psychological testing* (5th ed.). New York: Harper Collins Publisher, Inc.
- Ertmer, P. A. (2003). Transforming teacher education: Visions and strategies. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 51(1), 124–128.
- MirandaNet. (2000). *Teachers as innovators: An evaluation of the motivation of teachers to use ICT*. Preston, Cox & Cox.
- Molebash, P. (2001). Becoming an effective technology integration teacher: The effects of a technology-enriched elementary social studies methods course. Doctoral dissertation, University of Virginia.
- Aggarwal, J. C. (1996), *Essential of Educational Technology*, Vikas Publishing House, New Delhi.

- ICT in Education (2006). Information and communication technologies in teacher education: A planning guide.
- Kirwadkar, A & karanam, P. (2010) : E-learning Methodology. Sarup Book Publishers Pvt Ltd. New Delhi.
- Agarwal, J. P. (2013): Modern Educational Technology. Black Prints, Delhi.
- Venkataiah, N. (1995) "Educational Technology" Atul Publishers, daryaGanj, New Delhi.
- Goel, D. R. (2003), ICT in Education, Changes and Challenges in ICT in Education. M. S. University, Baroda.
- Vanaja, M. & Rajasekhar, S. (2009), Educational Technology and Computer Education, Neelkamal Publications Pvt. Ltd., Hyderabad.